

Combating corruption serves as the critical cornerstone for driving meaningful societal advancement

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Abstract. The fight against corruption remains one of the most pressing issues of today in the world. The fight against this evil covers many countries of the world. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also contributing to the fight against corruption. Currently, a number of programs have been adopted in our republic within the framework of the fight against corruption, and extensive work is being carried out on them. Within the framework of the fight against corruption, the Ministry of Justice has also developed a number of action plans, in which departments and institutions of the justice system are actively participating.

Key words: Corruption, civil society, UN Convention, tolerance

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, in his work "The City of Virtuous People," noted that one of the problems that hinders the development of civil society is corruption. Corruption is a cruel obstacle to the development of the market economy system, bilateral and multilateral cooperation between countries, business and investment. These "invisible hands" lie behind the opening and closing of dozens of joint ventures every year. It seems that the real reasons for the decrease in foreign investment in a country with a high level of corruption should be sought in this dangerous vice. As this issue deepens, first in the West, and then in Asian countries, and the area, scale and level of the "disease" in society are increasing, the constant question arises: what should be done? What can be done to reduce the scope of the impact of such a scourge that has taken over the world and is crippling the economies of countries?!

Corruption is a broad concept, and it is impossible to ignore the fact that it has become an everyday activity of certain layers, categories, and groups of society, interconnected and intertwined. Researchers have long been writing about the need for law enforcement agencies of the state to be more vigilant and astute in this "delicate", "complex" issue, as well as the need for non-governmental organizations, various commissions, journalists, and the independent judicial system to work more actively. Politicians, sociologists, psychologists, historians, state and public bodies, political parties, and most importantly, practitioners should analyze the issue and find a solution.

In recent years, articles on ways to combat corruption have begun to appear in the foreign press, including in the CIS countries. Analysis of studies conducted in the CIS member states shows that, despite the fact that thirty years have passed since we got rid of the Soviet system, the judiciary has still become an obedient organ of state power. The head of our state emphasizes this social weakness, a vicious vice in almost every speech. When we consider organizational issues at regional sessions, we first of all come across this issue. Bribery and corruption are hindering the

development of Uzbek society in every way, in particular, the process of democratic renewal and modernization. Despite the fact that this issue has been highlighted for many years and the “caught” officials have been shown on television and in the press, the vestiges of feudalism, greed, and bureaucracy that have seeped into the blood of the judiciary, prosecutor's office, heads of departments, and ordinary citizens are not disappearing from the life of our society. Corruption, firstly, leads to injustice, inequality and discontent of the population in society, which cannot but negatively affect the results of reforms in all areas; secondly, the insufficient level of legal awareness and legal culture among our citizens, their inability to protect their rights, increases the violation of the criterion of justice in society; thirdly, the democratic criterion in the form of political institutions and public organizations, although similar to the Western model, lags behind the requirements of the times in terms of content and essence, and this shortcoming prevents us from moving forward.

In our opinion, the role of one organization in this regard - the judicial authorities - should be strengthened and its privileges should increase. It is also the need of the hour for the newly established Anti-Corruption Agency to carry out all work together with the Ministry of Justice, fully ensuring the rule of law.

In accordance with Article 81 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption”, the Anti-Corruption Agency (hereinafter referred to as the Agency) is tasked with formulating and implementing state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption.

Within the framework of this task, the Agency coordinates the activities of ministries and departments in the field of preventing and combating corruption and organizes their joint and effective operation.

The Agency performs the following tasks in the field of implementing state policy in the field of combating corruption:

- develops and ensures the implementation of strategies and state programs to combat corruption;
- develops draft regulatory legal acts aimed at strengthening the legal framework for combating corruption;
- provides a systematic analysis of the state of corruption in the country, as well as studies areas with high corruption risks and the causes and conditions for committing corruption offenses;
- Ensures the implementation of the requirements of the UN Convention against Corruption, as well as implements systematic measures to develop international cooperation in this area, strengthen the country's image and increase its position in international rankings.
- Prepares an annual national report on the fight against corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Supports the activities of civil society institutions, the media and other representatives of the non-governmental sector in establishing public control over corruption.

Based on the analysis of the problems related to the human mind and worldview in the state and society, we still have a long way to go in the fight against the evil of corruption inherited from the former Soviet Union. The reason is that the hierarchical system, which works strictly from top to bottom, similar to that of China and Singapore, has not yet fully come into play. However, this natural process should not be artificially slowed down or “stopped” under pressure from certain

forces. In this regard, it is necessary to make good use of the rich experience of developed countries. For example, in the USA, reporter-journalists have established the most effective public control in the fight against corruption. In the CIS, including Uzbekistan, investigative journalism is in a shallow state and lags behind the needs of today. To be more precise, the defense of selfless journalists who conduct independent investigations, trying to expose the "dirt" of criminals, will not work. Even more regrettable, even if an article proving the secret wealth of a leader is published in the press, no firm measures are taken against it, and the situation does not change. For example, once upon a time, if a feuilleton was published about a leader, they would be expelled from the party, imprisoned, and that is why officials were afraid of the "fourth power."

So, if the activities of two or three powerful periodicals like "Mushtum" were supported and special programs were broadcast on television almost every day (whether there was a case of big or small greed), it is clear that many people would wake up. We believe that it is necessary to instill in the minds of citizens that there can be no development without criticism. The problem of instilling tolerance in the minds of adolescents and young people studying in the education system, a priority area in society, is looming before us. The idea that "the evil of corruption in society cannot be overcome" has been formed in the minds of young people (why it has not been formed in the minds of Japanese or Chinese citizens is a separate issue) is our biggest shortcoming.

If we do not make progress in this regard, the evil of corruption will continue to cast a shadow over the reputation of our nation. Unless we carry out more educational and propaganda work in the minds and souls of our sons and daughters in the family, kindergarten, and school that greed and bribery are not only a bad vice, but also the cause of the decline of our society and the backwardness of our economy, it will be difficult for us to achieve our goal. In recent years, the great idea that the state should serve the people, put forward by our President, has given civil society institutions the opportunity to develop systems and programs. However, for some reason, non-governmental non-profit organizations and political parties are delaying the implementation of initiatives and organizational work in this regard. True, recently, in particular, since 2017, the terms "parliamentary control" and "public control" have been introduced into our country, and the first laws on this issue have been adopted. So, we need to quickly create a functioning system in this area, taking into account the national mentality, and apply the advanced experience of Southeast Asian countries. Without public control, it is impossible to implement reforms of the political system in Uzbekistan. In particular, modernization, renewal, reforms and corruption do not "blend", there will be a constant struggle between supporters of innovation and old-fashionedness, science, innovation, creative thinkers and the old generation of bureaucracy.

First of all, the fight against corruption should start from the family. We believe that women have a great role in this regard. If our women can investigate the root cause of theft or bribery and speak their minds openly, then their husbands will undoubtedly start looking for honest livelihoods and find prosperity, peace and tranquility in their work and family. Corruption is the height of greed. To fight it, political will is required from officials. The way out of this situation is, first of all, to reduce the size of the state bureaucratic apparatus as much as possible, to minimize state interference in the personal lives and economic activities of citizens, and to eliminate monopolies.

True, the fight against corruption manifests itself differently in different countries. However, only two recipes are recognized in the world to avoid theft in the civil service: 1. Switzerland - reduce time. Of course, in our country, drastic measures are being taken to combat this vice.

Studies show that the most effective way to eliminate any evil is to fight its cause, not the evil itself. In our opinion, it is recommended to start the fight against this evil by solving the following problems: the agency should review the laws that are part of the corruption component; establish public control over state institutions (openness index); approve governors and ministers by the parliament and local councils; transfer all state services to the "Single Window" centers, strengthen the independence of the judiciary; social protection of civil servants, and ensure that the salaries of officials are 2-3 times higher than those in similar businesses (Georgian experience).

This requires the creation of independent commissions and centers, a serious study of the real situation, and the rapid start of work of a single center that will regularly collect all research and information. Because the work and tasks to be done will last for decades. It is worth recognizing that those involved in corruption in the public procurement, investment, banking, tax, customs, markets, and construction systems make good money. The extreme "weakness", "weakness", and even benevolence of legislative practice and law enforcement agencies in confronting them hinder our work, and as a result, there are more and more cases of people owning luxurious villas abroad in exchange for the appropriation of the underground and surface wealth of the people and the state.

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